

Studies on some Thioindigoids and Related Compounds: Part V.

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3-Hydroxy-6-bromo-thionaphthene has been condensed respectively with acenaphthenequinones, phenanthraquinone and three aromatic aldehydes. 6:6'-Dibromo-thioindigo has been prepared now from an authentic specimen of 3-hydroxy-6-bromo-thionaphthene. The resulting asymmetrical and symmetrical thioindigoids and thioindogenides of the 6-bromo series have been found lighter in colour than those of the corresponding products of the 7-bromo series previously reported. A combined study of colour, dyed shade on cotton and absorption maxima values of some of the 5-, 6- and 7-bromo dyes synthesised up till now, revealed that their colour change with respect to the parent dye stands in the manner: 5-Br dye > 7-Br dye > 6-Br dye > parent dye.

In this communication, 2-(6-bromo)-thionaphthene-acenaphthylene-indigos, 2-(6-and 5-bromo)-thionaphthene-9'-phenanthrene-indigos, 6: 6'-dibromo-thioindigo and benzylidene-2-(6-bromo)-thionaphthenes have been synthesised with the object of comparing their colour, dyed shade and absorption maxima with those of the corresponding isomeric 7- and 5-bromo^{1,2} compounds already studied.

The dyes of the acenaphthenequinone series, synthesised now are (Ia) 2-(6-bromo)-thionaphthene-, (Ib) 2-(6-bromo)-thionaphthene-8'-(3'-bromo)-, (Ic) 2-(6-bromo)-thionaphthene-8'-(1'-methoxy)-, (Id) 2-(6-bromo)-thionaphthene-8'-(3,4'-dinitro)-acenaphthylene-indigos, which are represented by the general formula I. These are brownish-red, violet-brown, and dark brownish-violet crystalline compounds produced in 62-77% yield. The dyes are soluble in nitrobenzene and glacial acetic acid; moderately soluble in benzene and carbon tetrachloride; slightly soluble in ethanol. The dyed shades on cotton are very well and uniformly developed except (Ic) from which lighter shade of the original dye was obtained. The colour of alkaline vat of (Id) is yellowish-brown and those of the other three is violet.

1. S. K. Guha and A. K. Mitra, *This Journal*, 1966, **43**, 597.
2. S. K. Guha and J. N. Chatterjea, *Chem. Ber*, 1959, **92**, 2768.

The two other asymmetrical dyes obtained are (IIa) 2-(6-bromo)-thionaphthene-, (IIb) 2-(5-bromo)-thionaphthene-9'-phenanthrene-indigos. These are respectively darkish violet and dark violet crystalline products. But the corresponding 2-(6-and 5-bromo)-thionaphthene-acenaphthylene-indigos (loc. cit.) are brownish-red and deep red respectively. Both the phenanthrene-indigos are soluble in xylene and nitrobenzene. The 6-bromo dye is soluble in glacial acetic acid where as the 5-bromo compound is moderately soluble in the same. In benzene and alcohol, the substance IIa is moderately soluble but the dye IIb is soluble in benzene and slightly soluble in ethanol. The dyed shade of these two products developed on cotton from an yellow alkaline vat at 60-70° was much lighter than the real shade of the compounds.

6:6'-Dibromo-thioindigo³ (III), Trade name, Thioindigo pink (Kalle & Co) was prepared next from a sample of 3-hydroxy-6-bromo-thionaphthene⁴. It separated from nitrobenzene in silky violet red crystals, m.p. above 300°. The dye is soluble in nitrobenzene; sparingly soluble in glacial acetic acid, carbon tetrachloride and benzene; insoluble in ethanol. It gives a pleasant green solution on treatment with cold strong sulphuric acid. (Lit⁵. recorded greenish-blue). An uniform attractive violet-red shade was developed on cotton from an alkaline yellow vat. (Lit⁵. recorded pink).

The thioindogenides, (IVa) benzylidene-, (IVb) 4'-nitro-benzylidene-, and (IVc) 4'-dimethylamino-benzylidene-2-(6-bromo)-thionaphthene are respectively light yellow, yellow and deep brownish-red crystalline substances; soluble in ethanol, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, acetone, acetic acid, benzene, nitrobenzene and xylene. Attempt to develop their dyed shade on cotton was not met with success. These possess the general structural formula (IV).

The colour, dyed shade on cotton and absorption maxima data of some of the thioindigoids and thioindogenides of the 6-bromo series mentioned in table II, on comparison with those of the corresponding 7-bromo compounds (table I), showed that 6-bromo dyes are lighter in colour than the 7-bromo products. This finding also led a step ahead to deduce the gradational change of colour of the isomeric 5-, 6-, and 7-bromo-thioindigoids and thioindogenides studied up till now with respect to their parent compound in the order 5-Br dye > 7-Br dye > 6-Br dye > parent dye.

3. B. P. 318, 595/1928; *British Chemical abstracts*. B. 1930, 897.

4. Ciba Ltd. Brit, 830, 223/1960., C.A. 1960, 54, 18550.

5. H. D. Hartough and S. L. Meisel. 'The Chemistry of Heterocyclic compounds'. Interscience Publishers Ltd., London., 1954, 7, 182.

TABLE I

Compounds	λ Xylene max
2-(5-bromo)-thionaphthene-AI	524 m μ
2-(7-bromo)-thionaphthene-AI	518
2-(6-bromo)-thionaphthene-AI	515
2-Thionaphthene-AI	477.5
2-(5-bromo)-thionaphthene-8'-(1'-methoxy)-AI	534
2-(7-bromo)-thionaphthene-8'-(1'-methoxy)-AI	526
2-(6-bromo)-thionaphthene-8'-(1'-methoxy)-AI	525
2-Thionaphthene-8'-(1'-methoxy)-AI	524
2-(5-bromo)-thionaphthene-9'-PI	556.5
2-(7-bromo)-thionaphthene-9'-PI	546
2-(6-bromo)-thionaphthene-9'-PI	545
2-Thionaphthene-9'-PI ⁶	540*
5:5'-Dibromo-thioindigo	562
7:7'-Dibromo-thioindigo	548
6:6'-Dibromo-thioindigo	547
Thioindigo	525
B-2-(5-bromo) thionaphthene	446
B-2-(7-bromo) thionaphthene	438
B-2-(6-bromo) thionaphthene	435
B-2-thionaphthene	434
4'-Dimethylamino-B-2-(5-bromo) thionaphthene	494
4'-Dimethylamino-B-2-(7-bromo)thionaphthene	490
4'-Dimethylamino-B-2-(6-bromo)thionaphthene	488
4'-Dimethylamino-B-2-thionaphthene	478

*D, Mandal, Ph.D. Thesis, The Bihar University, Muzaffarpur, India. 1957.

In tables I and II, AI, PI and B denote acenaphthylene-, phenanthrene-indigo and benzy-
lidene respectively. In table II, T denotes thionaphthene.

EXPERIMENTAL

3-Hydroxy-6-bromo-thionaphthene used here and previously for the synthesis of 3-indole-2'-(6'bromo)-thionaphthene-indigos⁷ was obtained following Guha and Mitra's method for 3-hydroxy-7-bromo-thionaphthene.¹

For convenience, the ten compounds synthesised here are described in Table II, where A and B₁ denote 3-hydroxy-6-, and 5-bromo-thionaphthene respectively.

The acenaphthylene-indigos, Ia-d, (Table II) were obtained from the reactants in glacial acetic acid (Ia in 60 ml. and Ib-d in 50 ml.) on treatment with strong HCl (2 ml.) and heating for 20 min. only. The dyes were crystallised from glacial acetic acid melting above 300°.

6. R. Pummerer and F. Luther, *Ber.* 1931, **641**, 831.

7. S. K. Guha and A. K. Mitra, *This Journal*, 1967, **44**, 694.

TABLE II

Compounds	Reactants (g)	Apparance; Yield (g); (%)	Action of H ₂ SO ₄	Shade on cotton	Formula	Analysis	
						Found	Reqd.
Ia. 2-(6-Bromo) T-AI.	Acenaphthene-quinone (0.182) + A (0.229)	Brownish-red; 0.31; (77.6)	Green	Yellowish-red	C ₂₀ H ₉ O ₂ BrS	C: 61.38% H: 2.42	61.08 2.3
Ib. 2-(6-Bromo) T-8'-(3'-bromo)-AI	3-bromo-acenaphthenequinone (0.261) + A (0.229)	Brownish-red; 0.35; (75)	Green (deeper than Ia)	Yellowish-red (deeper than Ia)	C ₂₀ H ₉ O ₂ Br ₂ S	C: 51.05 H: 1.94	50.87 1.71
Ic. 2-(6-Bromo) T-8'-(1'-methoxy)-AI	1-methoxy-acenaphthenequinone (0.212) + A (0.229)	Violet-brown 0.315; (74)	Darkish green	pink	C ₂₁ H ₁₁ O ₃ BrS	C: 60.29 H: 2.72	59.59 2.62
Id. 2-(6-Bromo) T-8'-(3':4'-dinitro)-AI	3:4-dinitro-acenaphthenequinone (0.272) + A (0.229)	Dark brownish-violet 0.396; (62)	Darkish brown	Darkish brown	C ₂₀ H ₇ O ₆ BrN ₂ S	N: 6.12 Br: 16.8	5.79 16.55
IIa. 2-(6-bromo) T-9'-PI	Phenanthraquinone (0.21) + A (0.229)	Darkish-violet 0.26; (62)	Light leaf green	Pink	C ₂₂ H ₁₁ O ₂ BrS	C: 63.41 H: 2.94	63.01 2.64
IIb. 2-(5-bromo) T-9'-PI	Phenanthraquinone (0.1) + B ₁ (0.11)	Dark violet; 0.09; (43)	Green	Light violet	C ₂₂ H ₁₁ O ₂ BrS	C: 63.26 H: 2.32	63.01 2.64
III. 6:6'-Dibromo-thioindigo	A(0.229) in NaOH soln. (10%; 25ml) and K ₃ Fe CN ₆ soln. (5%; 20 ml.)	Silky violet-red; 0.34; (76)	Pleasant green	Violet red	C ₁₆ H ₆ O ₂ Br ₂ S ₂	C: 42.56 H: 1.4	42.31 1.33
IVa. B-2-(6-bromo) T	benzaldehyde (0.11) + A (0.229)	Light yellow; 0.234; (73.7)	Yellowish-red		C ₁₅ H ₉ O BrS	C: 56.58 H: 2.93	56.79 2.86
IVb 4'-Nitro-B-2-(6-bromo)T	P-nitrobenzaldehyde (0.151) + A (0.229)	Yellow; 0.269; (74)	Light violet		C ₁₅ H ₈ O ₃ BrNS	N: 3.54 Br: 22.43	3.86 22.08
IVc. 4'-Dimethylamino-B-2(6-bromo)T	P-dimethylamino-benzaldehyde (0.149) + A (0.229)	Deep brownish red; 0.236; (65)	Violet-red		C ₁₇ H ₁₄ OBrNS	N: 3.65 Br: 21.88	3.88 22.21

The phenanthrene-indigos, IIa-b, were similarly prepared from the constituents in glacial acetic acid solution (IIa in 40 ml. and IIb in 5 ml.) and heating for 30 min. with the addition of a few drops of conc. HCl. The 6-bromo dye (IIa) crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 283-284° and the 5-bromo dye separated from nitrobenzene melting above 300°.

The thioindogenides, IV a-c, were obtained from the reactants in boiling anhydrous ethanolic solution (25 ml.) adding HCl (Conc. 1.5 ml.) and heating for 15 min. only. The compounds IVa, m.p. 154° and IVc m.p. 209° were crystallised from ethanol and IVb, m.p. 220° from glacial acetic acid.